

Prosodic Analysis: An Italian case study

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This study starts from the need to enhance the scientific knowledge on prosody features that characterize the human communication and in particular on the importance they have to attribute meaning to sentences. Starting from these considerations the focus of the paper is to distinguish the role that prosodic features have in distinguishing four different kinds of Italian sentences (statements, questions, commands, and exclamations). The methodology used for the analysis is the case study. 50 Italian users of the Institute of Research on Population and Social Policies (IRPPS) of the National Research Council of Rome participated in this study. Results of the case study showed different associations between the sentence types and tone types both for tonic and pre-tonic parts of the sentences.

Keywords: Prosody; Tonic; Pre-tonic; Duration; Intensity; Fundamental Frequency; Tone Units; Pitch

1. Introduction

Prosody represents a communication level used to reinforce and express the speaker intentions. The prosodic strategies are intentionally chosen by the speakers in order to reinforce their discourse construction. For instance, it is possible for the speaker to manipulate tone, rhythm, duration, accent and energy in a way that can be decisive in conveying an opinion in a political debate. Despite the importance assigned to prosodic features in attributing meaning to sentences, for a long time linguists have mostly investigated prosody in very limited domains (e.g., as indication of the interrogative or declarative kinds of the sentence). Although instrumental analyses have long been introduced in the study of phonetics and phonology of various languages, experimental investigations of prosody were not so common. The reason is due firstly to the difficulties to analyse prosodic aspect first of all because all the physical variables that determine it (e.g., the time and intensity of the pace and the f_0) are continuous without an a-priori segmentation. Second, because it is difficult to analyse the intonation that, clipped from its context, is totally devoid of meaning and function. In fact the

values that determine the prosody, and thus the intonation, are still fundamentally related, estimated and interpreted only in relation to what follows and what precedes prosodic units within the entire sentence. Therefore, if a vocal segment itself is considered, it is possible to extract in an objective way the height, the duration and the intensity; however, it is difficult to classify it into such specific categories as acute or severe, long or short, or intense or weak. A third difficulty in analysing the prosodic feature is due to its variability.

This study starts from the need to enhance the scientific knowledge on prosody features that characterize human communication and in particular on the importance they have to attribute meaning to sentences. The study focuses in particular on the Italian language and analyses how prosodic features differ among people. In particular three different prosodic features are analysed (namely, duration, f_0 , and intensity) in order to understand the role they have in distinguishing four different kinds of Italian sentences (statements, questions, exclamations, and commands). In particular the analysis of these parameters will allow defining associations between the sentences type and the tones. The methodology used for the analysis is the case study. To perform the analysis, 50 Italian users of the Institute of Research on Population and Social Policies (IRPPS) of the National Research Council of Rome were involved.

The paper is organized as follow: Section 2 gives an overview of the literature that exists in the prosodic field. Section 3 describes the method illustrating the parameters used for the prosodic analysis, the case study setting and implementation. Section 4 illustrates the results of the performed analysis. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper.

2. Background

The prosodic features give a relevant contribution to the construction of the meaning. On a prosodic level things present themselves differently, so it is very difficult to segment the prosodic continuum of discreet unities for various reasons:

- the prosodic traits often appear simultaneously and are combined in various ways, with complex interpretations not fully studied yet;
- the prosodic traits, furthermore, combine with segmented material in ways that, over time, are different;
- the prosodic facts, apart from carrying linguistic information properly, can also be used to transmit paralinguistic and extra linguistic information (e.g., emotions, speaker's attitudes and also personal characteristics such as age, sex, etc).

According to Werner & Keller (1994) four main levels of prosodic phenomena can be distinguished (as shown in Figure 1).

Figure 1. Main levels of prosodic phenomena.

On considering the first level (intention) the speaker can be assumed to use prosodic coding (other elements of speech) with a certain intention. This intention can influence linguistic (i.e., any oral expression using language signs) and paralinguistic expression (that is, non-verbal vocalizations such as onomatopoeia, expressions, speaking styles, etc.). Prosody clearly plays a major role in both types of phenomena. At the articulatory level, prosody is manifested as a series of modifications of articulatory movement; since it is fundamentally to be understood as a distinctive layer of phenomena superimposed on the normal articulatory speech train, it does not result in separate articulations. The acoustic realization level represents the emission of sound waves by muscle activity in the respiration system. These sound waves can be observed and quantified using prosodic acoustic parameters such as: f_0 , intensity, and duration. Finally, at the level of perception, it is possible to classify prosody in terms of the hearer's subjective experience (pauses, pitch/melody, length and loudness).

Only a few studies on prosody have been carried out through the careful measurement and precise experimental investigation of f_0 of the vocal folds. Studdert & Hadding (1973) underline the role of the f_0 contour in differentiating statements and questions. The perceptual judgments of questions or statements indicated that listeners were influenced by the entire f_0 contour and not just by the terminal f_0 . In the study conducted by Lieberman (1967) participants read questions and statements (with the same word order). Results underlined that questions were marked by a final rise in terminal f_0 whereas statements were characterized by a falling terminal f_0 . O'Shaughnessy (1979) analysed different sentences and identifies three critical regions: the first, medial, and last accented syllables of a question. He observed that "all three of these syllables are characterized by a rising f_0 contour, and concluded that the question intonation affects the f_0 contour of

the entire sentence, and is not limited to a rising contour at the end of the utterance". The same results are provided by Wright (1998) who carried out a study of the automatic recognition of twelve move types (e.g. reply to a question, wh-question, statement etc.) by using automatically extracted supra-segmental information. For this task three different models were used: Hidden Markov Model (HMM), Classification and Regression Trees, and Neural Networks. Vicsi & Szaszák (2008) analysed six types of basic sentence modalities (declarative, clauses before the closing clause enumerations, closing clause of a question to be complemented, yes-no question or closing clause of a yes-no question, imperative and exclamation sentences or closing clause of an imperative or exclamation sentence, Neutral). For the analysis an HMM based semantic level modality recognizer was developed with the aim of optimizing the parameters of the HMM modality. The recognizer underlined terminal falling tone contour in statements and a terminal rise for questions, exclamations and commands. Salmani Nodoushan and Birjandi (2005), too, summarized research that indicated f_0 contours can signal questions, statements, and emotional states (such as soothing, grumping, pleading, etc.).

On considering the Italian language only few studies have been developed on prosodic feature of the human-communication process (Zanuttini & Portner, 2003). In Benincà (1995, 1996), it is underlined that intonation is an important component to distinguish exclamations from statements.¹ Benincà states that while statements are characterised by a terminal falling tonal contour, the prosodic aspects of the exclamations consist of high accent and finish with a rise tonal contour. Different results for exclamations are provided by Delattre (1966) and D'Eugenio (1976) who observed a rising-falling tonal trend for exclamations in their studies. The same results are underlined by Moraes (2008) that observe, for the Brazilian Portuguese, that exclamations, introduced by a wh-word, have a tonal trend similar to that of the wh questions, characterized by a initial rise tone level and by a progressive falling tone trend. The studies conducted by Avesani and Vayra (2005) and Grice, D'Imperio, Savino and Avesani (2005) are the only ones focused on intonation for Italian Florentine dialect. According to them, the prosodic aspects of the exclamations consist of a rise in initial tone contour with a high accent and finish with a falling tonal contour. Nevertheless, Cruttenden (1981) considered that tone trend of exclamations is occasional, even rare. In this connection, Bolinger (1989, p. 249) stated that "the connection between intonation and exclamation must be both broad and deep." Along the same lines, O'Connor and Arnold (1973, p. 89) stated that "

¹ See also Salmani Nodoushan and Birjandi (2005) for Persia and English languages

.. no tone group is used exclusively with this or that sentence type ... and also that no sentence type always requires the use of one and only one tone group." This consideration is probably based on the erroneous conclusion that assert that the melody of exclamations would be virtually the same as statement, characterized by a falling tone contour. This consideration is also reported by Canepari (2003), that underlines that even the final tone contour of statements and exclamations, is the same (falling tone), but they are not equal as the exclamation presents an initial rising tone contour that is not present in statements. Equally important are the studies conducted by Canepari (1985), Magno Caldognetto, Ferrero, Lavagnoli and Vaggés (1978), Endo and Bertinetto (1997), Mascaró (1986), Prieto (1998), Pradilla e Prieto (2002) and Salcioli (1988). By analysing the parameters of f_0 , duration and intensity, they all observed a falling-rising tonal trend for questions. Appendix A summarises the results of these studies.

3. Method

To conduct the current study, the case study methodology was used. The case study is based on "an in-depth investigation of a single individual or groups and it provides a systematic way of looking at events, analyzing information, collecting data and reporting the results needed" (Feagin, Orum, & Sjöberg, p. 28). Abercrombie, Hill and Turner (1984, p. 34) define the case study as "the detailed examination of a single example of a class of phenomena, a case study cannot provide reliable information about the broader class, but it may be useful in the preliminary stages of an investigation since it provides hypotheses, which may be tested systematically with a larger number of cases." In order to analyse the role that prosodic features have in distinguishing four different kinds of Italian sentences (statements, questions, exclamations and commands) a case study has been implemented. To perform the study 50 Italian users of the Institute of Research on Population and Social Policies (IRPPS) of the National Research Council of Rome have been involved. In the following section the study setting, implementation, and results are described in detail.

3.1. Parameters used for the prosodic analysis

3.1.1. Duration, intensity, and f_0

In terms of phonetic realization, the physical properties of the voice, on prosodic level, are associated with the following parameters:

- duration
- intensity
- f_0

The duration of the phonic segment, measured in seconds and fractions of a second (milliseconds), conveys the impression of its length. The length of the phone within the syllable is directly related to the speed of speech. The distinction between perception of the length of phones is not based on absolute values of duration, but the relationship that exists between the durations of phones within the communication process (Savy, Crocco & Giordano, 2000).

The intensity is the measurable factor corresponding to the loudness of the sound. It is measured in levels of energy (dB) and its value can vary with changes in air pressure for exhalation. The intensity can be manipulated for various purposes for example it is possible for the speaker to increase the volume of the voice to express anger during a discussion to attract the attention of the listener. The role of the intensity was taken for granted for a long time until a few decades ago, and many experiments had failed to show the absolute importance of this parameter mainly in defining and identifying of syllabic units (Petrillo, 2000).

The f_0 —also known as (perceptual) pitch—of the voice is the result of vibration of vocal cords, involved in the production of vowels and consonants. The speed of the vibration depends on the mass, tension and length of the vocal cords. The unit to measure the f_0 is the Hertz (Hz) that indicates the number of cycles of vibration per second. Children and women have higher voice frequencies than men. According to Cruttenden (1986), while the average band frequency (range) for adult males extends between 60 Hz and 240 Hz, for women it is between 180 and 400 Hz; Laver (1994) shows different values for the frequency range of male adults (50 to 250 Hz) and women (120-480 Hz). Obviously, these only represent average values which cannot be generalized and applied to all individual speakers or to the whole communication process. Many authors use the term pitch to indicate the f_0 . Bolinger (1958), for instance, uses the term perceptual pitch instead of f_0 . He stated that "pitch has only one ingredient, the fundamental frequency of the voice" (p. 110). More generally, the confusion between the two terms is due to the complex relations between acoustic and perceptive aspects of pitch.

3.1.2. Sentence classification

A sentence classification in natural language is based on the sentence meaning. Following this criterion, it is possible to distinguish four different classes of semantic categories for Italian natural language sentences. These classes are:

- **Statements** (Declarative): These are sentences that can be judged as true or false without ambiguity. The truth or falsity of the declarative

sentences is known as the truth condition. For a sentence to be a statement, it is not necessary that we actually know whether it is true or false, but it must be clear that it is one or the other. A statement is distinct from a sentence in that a sentence is only one formulation of a statement, whereas there may be many other formulations expressing the same statement. An example of a statement sentence is: *Anna parlerà con Maria oggi* (Anna will speak with Maria today).

- **Questions** (Interrogative): These sentences may be introduced by (1) a pronoun or adjective question (e.g., *Dove sei andato?* (Where did you go?); *Quante mele hai comprato?* (How many apples did you buy?)) or (2) by a question which we answer with a yes or a no (e.g., *Hai mangiato?* (Have you eaten?)).
- **Exclamations** (Exclamative): These sentences express rich emphasis within the clause (e.g., *Che sfortuna abbiamo avuto!* (What bad luck we had!)).
- **Commands** (Comandi): These sentences do not have an overt grammatical subject and have the verb in the imperative form as (e.g., *Parla con Maria oggi* (Speak to Maria today)).

Starting from this classification, the study will test the following hypothesis: “sentence types may be distinguished through the analysis of prosodic features.”

For the prosodic analysis, a model is used, which supposes that a sentence is built from distinctive sequence of tone units (TU). TU can consist of a single word or a number of words. The whole TU stands between double vertical bars (lines) || while longer TU are separated from each other's by pauses which are marked by a single vertical line |. The following examples illustrate sentences composed of different TU:

|| The workers | usually start work | very early in the morning || They usually start at six ||.

To identify the boundary markers of the TU within the sentence the following parameters described by Caputo (1991) and Savy (1999) were used:

- presence of pauses
- prepausal lengthening
- declination of intonation

The first widely considered criterion is the presence of pauses. The pauses can be distinguished in periods of silence, hesitations (such as “mhm”, “Ehh”,

etc.) or long extension of the last vowel of the word. The relative slowdown of the speech, known as “prepausal lengthening” is one of the most frequent parameters present in spontaneous speech communication. A frequent example that is strictly linked to this parameter is the strong decrease of intensity and f_0 in the last part of the tonic unit. For most cases this decrease brings values below the dominant range.

Finally the declination of intonation indicates the global trend of gradual lowering of f_0 and intensity values along the sentence. Within the sentence the flow of the intensity and f_0 undergoes several changes during phonation, which include ups and downs as well as increases and decreases, but it still presents a gradual decline that is shown by a two brand border.

By means of TU, speakers signal whether to proclaim, refer, agree, disagree, hesitate, question or indicate continuation and completion of turn-taking in speech. Each TU has movement, of rhythm and music associated with the pitch of the voice (Roach, 1983). This certain pattern of voice movement is called ‘tone’.

There are many authors who have identified different types of tones. Crystal (1969) cited in Ladefoged (1975), identified four basic tone types (falling, rising-falling, rising, and falling-rising); Brazil, Coulthard, and Johns (1980) and Roach (1983) classified tones in five types (fall, rise, rise-fall, fall-rise, and level). For the Italian language, Lepschy (1978) identified five tones types: discendete (falling), ascendente (rising), costante (level), discendete-ascendente (falling-rising), and ascendente- discendete (rising-falling). What makes a tone falling or rising is the direction of the f_0 movement on the last stressed (tonic) syllable. Halliday defines the tonic syllable as “the stressed syllable of the last accented word in an intonational phrase” (Halliday, 1967, p. 208). He provides a distinction between the pre-tonic and tonic parts of the sentence, and defines the pre-tonic as ‘the part before the last sentence accent’ and the tonic as ‘the remainder part’. In the English language the most important tonal movement often occurs on the last tonic syllable, but it can also be found before that (Ladefoged, 1993). In fact the most prominent syllable in the tonal group is not predictable, as it depends on the prominence given by the speaker based on what he/she considers most important to emphasize. In the Figure 2 the pre-tonic and tonic parts of the yes/no question “Did the jumper slide off the chair?” (extracted from Vonwiller, King, Stevens and Latimer (1990)) are shown.

Figure 2: The pre-tonic and tonic parts of the yes/no question "Did the jumper slide off the chair?" (Vonwiller, King, Stevens and Latimer, 1990).

According to Halliday, the tonic component is always present in a sentence while the pre-tonic component may be absent. Moreover the tonic component can come in two different parts. This is the case of the command sentence "Do slide the jumper off the chair" shown in the following Figure 3.

Figure 3: The tonic part of the command sentence "Do slide the jumper off the chair" (Vonwiller, King, Stevens and Latimer, 1990)

A fall in f_0 on the tonic syllable renders the tone as falling, while a rising tone is one in which the tonic syllable is the start of an upward glide of f_0 . As such, in this study only the TU containing tonic and pre-tonic parts was considered for the analysis. In particular for defining the tonic part of the sentence, the following criteria adopted from Caputo (1993) were used for identifying accent dominance in sentences:

- significant change in f_0 within vowels
- intensity level of TU (i.e., high, medium or low)
- melodic range within which any changes occur
- relative duration of vowels and syllables within TU
- listening test

The tone types to associate with the tonic and pre-tonic parts of a sentence are those described by Lepschy (1978) for the Italian language:

- Tone 1 fall/falling (*discendente*),
- Tone 2 rise/rising (*ascendente*);
- Tone 3 level (*costante*);
- Tone 4 fall-rise/falling-rising (*discendente-ascendente*);
- Tone 5 rise-fall/rising-falling (*ascendente-discendente*).

To facilitate the understanding of this tone type classification, a graphical representation of the intonation contours associated with each of the tones is provided in the Figure 4.

TONE	INTONATION CONTOUR
1	
2	
3	
4	
5	

The different tone types that characterise the tonic and pre-tonic parts of each Italian sentence used for the analysis have been identified in order to define the intonation patterns that characterise the different kinds of sentences. Intonational patterns are defined as the sequences of the tone types that characterise both the tonic and pre-tonic parts of any given sentence. For instance, let us suppose that a sentence has a pre-tonic part with falling tone and a tonic part with rising tone; the intonational patterns of the sentence will be Tone 4.

Figure 4. Graphical illustration of intonation contours.

3.2. Case study setting an implementation

To conduct the study 50 Italian speakers (N=50) grouped into male and female sub-groups (F=32 and M=18 with the age range 25 to 60 years), all users of the Institute of Research on Population and Social Policies (IRPPS) of the National Research Council of Rome helped us. The Record-Pad Sound Recorder² system, with the support of a microphone was used to record the sentences. For the analysis of the different prosodic features the PRAAT³ system with a plug-ins that adds INTSINT model was used. Before starting the test, each participant was given a list with the different sentences that have to be pronounced (each participant was asked to pronounce 12 sentence, i.e., 3

² <http://www.nch.com.au/recordpad/index.html>

³ <http://www.fon.hum.uva.nl/praat/>

for each sentence (statements, questions, exclamations and commands); the sentences were selected from the Internet.

The case study implementation involved two different steps. The first step consisted of an explanation to participants of both the case study objectives and the modalities to use the microphone to record the sentences. In the second step, each participant, one at a time, pronounced the different sentences following the instructions written in the list. For each sample the PRAAT system returned the sound wave and spectrogram of the sentence (as illustrates in Figure 5). The curve in blue shown in the Figure 5 represents the f_0 while the curve in yellow indicates the intensity.

Figure 5. Sound wave and spectrogram of the sentence produced by the PRAAT system.

The first step of the analysis was to identify the TU within each sentence according to the parameters described above (duration, f_0 and intensity). This was performed by using the INTSINT model. The symbols used for the identification of TU boundaries are the square brackets. Therefore at this stage the symbol [is inserted at the beginning of the first segment of the TU, while the symbol] is placed at the end of last segment of the TU. After the TU has been detected, the identification of the main accent based on the criteria defined by Caputo (previously described) was carried out to separate the tonic and then the pre-tonic part of each TU. In particular the measurement of the intensity value within each TU and the duration of vowels and syllables were automatically extracted from the system, while the measurement of the f_0 values on the vowels was carried out manually on the alignment of f_0 on

each vowel. When f_0 presented a static trend at the vowel only one value was observed in a medium position within the 'boundaries' of the vowel. When, the trend was revealed as dynamic values at the points of change were measured. For instance, in Figure 6 (below) the TU "Ora disegna un mezzo cerchio" extracted from the corpus is illustrated.

Figure 6. TU targets of the sentence "Now draw a half circle".

The main accent is assigned to the noun "disegna" where f_0 and also intensity maximums are observed. So the sentence is characterized by pre-tonic and tonic parts as shown. In particular on the stylized curve a sequence of tonal "targets" (i.e. points where the f_0 values are significant and important for the evolution of the curve) is identified. Each target is identified in relation to the previous point of the curve. The first possibility is that the change to label is a local change:

- Higher,
- Lower,
- Same (i.e., equal in height compared to the previous target),
- Downstepping (slightly lower), or
- Upstepping (slightly higher)

Usually, 'Higher' and 'Lower' mark a peak and a trough, respectively; as such, the targets are higher or lower not only with respect to the previous targets, but also to the following ones. Instead, the 'Downstepping' may be higher by one point following (in descending a piece of tonal profile) and Upstepping lower than a target following (in an upward movement). The second possibility is that the target refers to:

- Top (the highest point of TU), or
- Bottom (the lowest point of the TU)

For the transcription, the initials of each label: H, L, S, D, U, T, B have been

used for ease of reference. Also targets at TU boundaries are labeled. The starting point of the TU is taken in a special position for lack of a previous target to reference and therefore can be:

- Top: [T
- Bottom: [B

The last targets of TU may be T] B] H] L] U] D], but if it does not presents a particularly strong value, it is labeled with single brackets] (e.g., Figure 6 above).

The analysis of the f₀ trend allowed defining criteria to classify each TU according to the different tone types defined by Lepschy (1978). Tables 1, 2, 3, and 4 show these criteria for each tone types extracted from the analysis. The value “level” doesn’t appear in any of the analysed sentences so it was not possible to extract criteria for this value.

Table 1.

TU Targets: Extracted Criteria for Fall Tone

 TONE TYPE: FALL

B follows T this is the primary condition for classifying the TU trend as “fall”.

T is at the beginning of the TU this refers not necessarily to the first syllable, but to the first syllables: at least three for TU, around 10-12 syllables.

B is at the end of the TU within the last syllables.

H or U do not present the same values of T.

L or D do not present the same values of B.

Table 2.

TU Targets: Extracted Criteria for Rise Tone

 TONE TYPE: RISE

B precedes T.

B is at the beginning or at the end of the curve.

T is at the end of the curve.

Table 3.

Extracted Criteria for Fall-Rise Tone

 TONE TYPE: FALL-RISE

B is in the center of the TU.

T is at the beginning or at the end of the curve.

Opposed to T there is an H or a U with the same or almost value of T.

H and L do not present the same values of T.

Table 4.

Extracted Criteria for Rise-Fall Tone

STONE TYPE: RISE-FALL
T is in the middle of the TU.
B is at the beginning or at the end of the curve.
B or any point low as B comes before T.
H and L do not present the same values of T and B.

The extracted tone types values have been considered both for the pre-tonic part and the tonic part of the sentences.

4.Results

All in all, 600 sentences were analyzed. Each of the analysed sentences has been associated with the different criteria for each tone type extracted from the previous analysis, and was associated both with the pre-tonic and the tonic part of the sentences. Starting from the values of the couple (pre-tonic and tonic) provided by the INTSINT model, two different associations between the 'statement' sentence type and the couple resulted from the analysis as illustrated in Table 5.

Table 5.

Associations Between the 'Statements' Sentence Type and the Couple of Values

Associations	FIRST		SECOND	
	PRE-TONIC	TONIC	PRE-TONIC	TONIC
Tone type	Fall	Fall-Rise	Fall-Rise	Rise-fall
User %	74%		26%	

The majority (74%) of the users (37 users, 25 male and 12 female) belonged to the first association that had a couple equal to fall, fall-rise. 26% of the users (13 users, 7 male and 6 female) belonged to the second association that had a couple equal to fall-rise, rise-fall.

On considering the 'questions', three different associations were extracted from the analysis as illustrated in Table 6.

Table 6.

Associations Between the 'Questions' Sentence Type and the Couple of Values

Associations	FIRST		SECOND		THIRD	
	PRE-TONIC	TONIC	PRE-TONIC	TONIC	PRE-TONIC	TONIC
Tone type	Fall	Rise	Rise-fall	Fall	Fall	Fall
User %	52%		28%		20%	

The majority (52%) of the users (26 users, 17 male and 9 female) belonged to

the first association that had a couple equal to (fall, rise). 20% of the users (14 users, 9 male and 51 female) belonged to the second association that had a couple equal to rise-fall, fall. Finally, 28% of the users (10 users, 6 male and 4 female) belonged to the third association that had a couple equal to fall, fall.

With respect to the 'exclamations', three different associations were extracted from the analysis as illustrated in Table 7.

Table 7

Associations Between 'Exclamation' Sentence Type and the Couple of Values

Associations	FIRST		SECOND		THIRD	
	PRE-TONIC	TONIC	PRE-TONIC	TONIC	PRE-TONIC	TONIC
Tone type	Rise	Rise	Rise-fall	Rise-fall	Rise	Fall-rise
User %	78%		20%		2%	

The majority (78 %) of the users (39 users, 24 male and 15 female) belonged to the first association that had a couple equal to rise, rise. 20 % of the users (10 users, 7 male and 3 female) belonged to the second association that had a couple equal to rise-fall, rise-fall. Moreover, 2 % of the users (1 male user) belonged to the third association that had a couple equal to rise, fall-rise.

Finally, on considering the 'command' sentence type, three different associations were extracted from the analysis as illustrated in Table 8.

Table 8

Associations between the "Commands" sentence type and the couple of values

Associations	FIRST		SECOND		THIRD	
	PRE-TONIC	TONIC	PRE-TONIC	TONIC	PRE-TONIC	TONIC
Tone type	Rise-fall	Fall	Fall	Fall-rise	Fall-rise	Fall
User %	58%		34%		8%	

The majority (58 %) of the users (29 users, 19 male and 10 female) belonged to the first association that had a couple equal to rise-fall, fall. 34 % of the users (17 users, 11 male and 6 female) belonged to the second association that had a couple equal to fall, fall-rise. Finally, 8 % of the users (4 users, 2 male and 2 female) belongs to the third association that had a couple equal to fall-rise, fall.

5. Conclusion

The results of this case study showed different associations between sentences types and the tone types both for tonic and pre-tonic parts of the sentences for different people participating in the case study. In particular the case study highlighted two different associations between 'statement' sentences type and the tone type: (a) fall and fall-rise, and (b) fall-rise and

rise-fall. With respect to 'questions', three different associations resulted from the analysis: (a) fall-rise, (b) rise-fall and fall, and (c) fall and fall. Three different associations were extracted for 'exclamations': (a) rise and rise, (b) rise-fall and rise-fall, and (c) rise and fall-rise. For 'commands' three associations were found: (a) rise-fall and fall, (b) fall and fall-rise, and (c) fall and rise-fall.

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Appendix A. Studies on Prosody for Sentence Recognition

Studdert & Hadding (1973) Lieberman (1967) Wright (1998)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • statements, • questions, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • f0 at the stress, • perceived terminal guide • energy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • terminal fall and/or low stress in statements, • terminal rise and/or high stress in questions.
Vicsi & Szaszák (2008)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • statements, • questions, • commands, • exclamations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • energy, • f0. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • terminal fall in statements, • terminal rise for questions, exclamations and commands.
Benincà (1995, 1996)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • statements, • exclamations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • duration, • intensity, • f0. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • terminal fall and/or low stress in statements, • terminal rise for exclamations
Delattre (1966) D'Eugenio (1976) Moraes (2008) Avesani & Vayra (2005) Grice et al. (2005) O Connor & Arnold (1973)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • exclamations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • f0 • energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • rise-fall tonal trend.
Cruttenden (1981)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • statements, • exclamations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • energy, • f0. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • terminal fall.
Bolinger (1989)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • exclamations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • f0 at the stress, • energy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the connection between intonation and exclamation must be both broad and deep.
Canepari (2003)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • statements, • exclamations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • f0, • duration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • terminal fall in both statements and exclamations but exclamations present a rise-fall tonal trend.
Canepari (1985) Magno Caldognetto et al. (1978) Endo e Bertinetto (1997) Mascaró (1986) Prieto (1998) Pradilla e Prieto (2002) Salcioli (1988)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • questions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • f0, • duration, • intensity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fall-rise tonal trend .